

ISic1475

I.Sicily inscription 1475

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

funerary

monument

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2013.10.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Helorus

Place of origin (modern)

Eloro

Provenance

contrada Ficopala, 1km NE of S. Paolo train station

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 49366 + 49367 + 49368

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644985

Bibliography

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 99 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 197-200 fig.3
Arena, R. 1998. Iscrizioni greche arcaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. V. Iscrizioni
di Taranto, Locri Epizefiri, Velia e Siracusa. Alessandria. At no.75

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